

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020
programme of the European Union

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OUR LOGO

The multi-coloured logo is the primary brand mark for IN-HABIT. In the following pages, you'll learn how the logo can be used to ensure consistency across all touchpoints.

[Download the IN-HABIT logos: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

The dark blue logo is the correct logo for formal situations of the IN-HABIT identity.

[Download the IN-HABIT logos: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

In addition to the primary and secondary logos, the following colourways can also be used for the logo.

[Download the IN-HABIT logos: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

LIGHT BLUE

RED

YELLOW

GREEN

BLACK

WHITE

The protected area keeps the IN-HABIT logo free from other text or graphic elements that could compromise its legibility or recognition. The height of the H from the IN-HABIT logo should be used to define the protected area around the margins.

Coloured versions of the IN-HABIT logo should **not** be used over a coloured background or image. In these situations, use the white version.

COLOUR BACKGROUND

The white version of the IN-HABIT logo must be used over a coloured background.

IMAGE BACKGROUND

The white version of the IN-HABIT logo must be used over images.

Example of incorrect use of the primary logo over an image

Below are some IN-HABIT logo application examples that follow the rules set out on the previous page.

POWERPOINT DOCUMENT

Example of the primary IN-HABIT logo being used in a PowerPoint document

WORD DOCUMENT

Example of the primary IN-HABIT logo being used in the header of a Word document

SOCIAL MEDIA ASSET

Example of the white IN-HABIT logo being used over an image for use on social media

Below are some violations of the brand guidelines.
Note: these examples don't cover all possible violations.

Do **not** stretch or distort the logo

Do **not** apply a different colour to the logo to those described in this chapter

Do **not** change the position of any of the logo's elements

Do **not** overlay graphic elements or text over the logo

Do **not** use a gradient background that compromises the logo's legibility

Do **not** apply a gradient to the logo

Do **not** apply a drop shadow to the logo

Do **not** recreate the primary logo in grayscale

IN-HABIT is co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union and, where appropriate, this should be communicated on brand material via the EU flag and associated copy below. There are two versions:

[Download the EU flag graphics: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

[Read the EU communication toolkit: https://bit.ly/2NGdeER](https://bit.ly/2NGdeER)

CO-FUNDED (WHITE BACKGROUND)

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union

GRANT (WHITE BACKGROUND)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

CO-FUNDED (COLOURED BACKGROUND OR IMAGE)

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union

GRANT (COLOURED BACKGROUND OR IMAGE)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

The EU flag and accompanying text can be used over photography where there is enough reasonable contrast between the text and the image to make the text legible.

The EU flag and accompanying text should be used over a brand colour when overlaying over photography where there is **not** enough contrast between the text and the image to make the text legible.

The EU flag and accompanying text should **not** be used over photography where there is not enough contrast between the text and the image to make the text legible.

The EU flag and accompanying text should be displayed in all IN-HABIT brand documents such as PowerPoint presentations and Word documents.

POWERPOINT DOCUMENT

The EU flag features at the bottom of each PowerPoint slide

WORD DOCUMENT

The EU flag features in the footer on every page of a Word document

OUR COLOURS

The IN-HABIT primary colours should be the dominant colours used throughout IN-HABIT material. IN-HABIT Formal Blue should be used in formal situations and applications of the IN-HABIT identity.

The CMYK colour values should be used for print applications. The RGB colour values should be used for digital applications. The HEX colour values should be used for web-based applications. Note, the CMYK colours used in print applications will look different compared to the RGB colours used digitally.

IN-HABIT BLUE

CMYK 78 24 0 8
 RGB 36 173 234
 HEX #24ADEA

IN-HABIT RED

CMYK 0 85 92 0
 RGB 239 68 65
 HEX #EF4441

IN-HABIT YELLOW

CMYK 00 00 00 00
 RGB 249 203 88
 HEX #F9CB58

IN-HABIT GREEN

CMYK 60 0 63 0
 RGB 53 229 149
 HEX #35E595

IN-HABIT FORMAL BLUE

CMYK 70 33 0 57
 RGB 33 73 109
 HEX #21496D

BLACK

CMYK 40 40 40 100
 RGB 0 0 0
 HEX #000000

WHITE

CMYK 0 0 0 0
 RGB 255 255 255
 HEX #FFFFFF

The IN-HABIT secondary colours are used for the IN-HABIT brand icons and can also be used as accent colours across various IN-HABIT material.

The CMYK colour values should be used for print applications. The RGB colour values should be used for digital applications. The HEX colour values should be used for web-based applications. Note, the CMYK colours used in print applications will look different compared to the RGB colours used digitally.

LIGHT BLUE

CMYK 83 42 0 0
 RGB 0 126 198
 HEX #007EC6

LIGHT RED

CMYK 9 100 46 2
 RGB 213 2 83
 HEX #D50253

LIGHT YELLOW

CMYK 0 44 71 0
 RGB 249 164 84
 HEX #F9A454

LIGHT GREEN

CMYK 69 0 69 0
 RGB 6 211 122
 HEX #06D37A

DARK BLUE

CMYK 100 86 39 30
 RGB 2 42 90
 HEX #022A5A

DARK RED

CMYK 0 82 51 0
 RGB 249 75 92
 HEX #F94B5C

DARK YELLOW

CMYK 0 67 94 0
 RGB 255 109 1
 HEX #FF6D01

DARK GREEN

CMYK 91 36 100 34
 RGB 0 91 35
 HEX #005B23

Each city has a primary IN-HABIT brand colour assigned to it based on the dominant colour of the country's flag. This should be the dominant colour use for any city-specific material (for example, backgrounds of text boxes and accent colour).

NITRA (SLOVAKIA)LIGHT BLUE

RIGA (LATVIA)RED

CORDOBA (SPAIN)YELLOW

LUCCA (ITALY)GREEN

OUR TYPOGRAPHY

The primary typeface for all IN-HABIT materials is Nunito. Where it's not possible to use Nunito, Calibri should be used. Note: Nunito and Calibri should **never** be used together in any application.

[Download the Nunito brand fonts: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

PRIMARY TYPEFACE

NUNITO

REGULAR

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

BOLD

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

FALLBACK TYPEFACE

CALIBRI

REGULAR

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

BOLD

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

Nunito Bold should always be used for titles and short bits of text that need to stand out. Nunito Regular should always be used for body copy. The same applies to Calibri, if Nunito can't be used.

TITLE TEXT

Titles should be set in **all caps** and **bold** weight.

Body text

Body text should be set in **sentence case** and **regular** weight.

The slide features a blue header with the 'IN-HABIT' logo in the top left corner. The main content area is white with a large, faint, light-blue abstract graphic of interconnected circles and lines on the right side. The text is arranged as follows:

- TITLE GOES HERE** (in all caps, bold weight)
- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Praesent tortor lectus, laoreet a laoreet ac, vulputate id libero. Nunc nulla nunc, blandit nec sem a, consectetur venenatis nisi. Integer sit amet tempus nibh. Suspendisse ac condimentum libero. Nunc hendrerit mi ac aliquam posuere.

At the bottom left, there is a small European Union logo and text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 695227". The number "3" is in the bottom right corner.

Example PowerPoint presentation slide

OUR ICONS

We have a suite of brand icons that can be used to help illustrate and visualise information throughout the various brand applications.

🔗 **Download the brand icons:** <https://bit.ly/3cpodwL>

Note, we have a suite of brand icons available in a PowerPoint template for immediate use.

The brand icons are available to use in the following brand colours.

BLUE

RED

YELLOW

GREEN

BLACK

WHITE

The icon(s) can be any of the brand colours stated on the previous page (except for white) when used on a white background.

The icon(s) should always be white when used over a coloured background and image.

Example of an icon being used in a PowerPoint presentation

Example of icons being used in a PowerPoint presentation

OUR PATTERN

Our brand pattern can be used across various brand applications.

[Download the brand patterns: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

MULTICOLOURED PATTERN

YELLOW

GREEN

RED

LIGHT BLUE

DARK BLUE

Our brand pattern can be used as a background across various brand applications.

PATTERN USE

Example of the multicoloured pattern being used in a PowerPoint presentation

Where text is laid over the top of a pattern, a text box in one of the brand colours must be used with white text.

Don't overlay text over the brand pattern without a coloured text box behind the text

Similarly, the graphic that makes up the pattern can be used on its own as a background across various brand applications.

GRAPHIC USE

Example of the graphic being used in a PowerPoint presentation

The graphic can also be used at 10% opacity of any of the brand colours.

Don't use a text colour that doesn't have reasonable contrast with the pattern or graphic colour behind it

OUR IMAGES

Along with the use of the brand colours and icons, image use is an integral part of the IN-HABIT brand identity. Images can convey a message or a mood within the overall IN-HABIT brand and should focus on people or places.

🔗 Download brand images: <https://bit.ly/3cpodwL>

Where high-quality stock imagery use isn't possible, "home made" imagery use is allowed where the image is authentic and personable.

Generic stock images that aren't authentic shouldn't be used.

Images can be used standalone or paired with text as a background. If pairing with text, the text must always be clearly legible.

Where images are used for backgrounds with text laid over the top, a text box in one of the brand colours must be used with white text.

Example of an image being used in a PowerPoint presentation

BRAND APPLICATIONS

The IN-HABIT visual identity and graphic package includes:

VISUAL GUIDELINES

A simple tool with examples on how to use logos and imagery, along with dos and don'ts. This how-to guide will help creating consistent projects in line with the IN-HABIT brand.

OUR LOGOS

Our logos in the colours of the project palette, and black and white; both in high and low resolution.

OUR ICONS

Our icons in the colours of the project palette, and black and white; both in high and low resolution.

OUR PATTERN

Our patterns to be used as background designs for your communication.

NUNITO

OUR TYPOGRAPHY

Our typeface/font.

EU FLAG

The EU flag both in colour and black and white, including the project funding information.

IMAGES

Free images for you to use on your presentations.

The IN-HABIT visual identity and graphic package includes templates in the following formats:

DOCUMENT TEMPLATES

- Press release
- Report
- Meeting agenda
- Meeting minutes
- Deliverable
- Letterhead
- Simple text (free form)

Available in two formats:

- Microsoft Word: downloadable for offline work.
- Google Drive: for documents requiring contribution from many partners. By reducing the number of saved versions, we reduce the potential for errors.

PRESENTATION TEMPLATES

- Formal presentation (for example, for external meetings, conferences, etc.)
- Informal presentation (for internal meetings, etc.)

Available in two formats:

- Lighter version, for download
- Complete version, for online use (like Teams, Drive or other collaborative spaces)
- Icon library (separated - for easier, lighter use)

All templates have been tested and work correctly across several devices. In the folder, you will also find a “how to” guide showing how to add icons, etc. to these templates.

Media-rich presentations are an effective way to connect with your audience. Including high-quality images often adds hugely to audience engagement, but it also increases file size. That means your presentation or file could be too large for some email servers, and it could run a lot slower on some computers.

POWERPOINT DOCUMENT

To reduce image size in Microsoft PowerPoint:

1. Select a picture, go to the “**Format**” tab and select “**Picture Tools**”.
2. Choose “**Compress Pictures**” in the top left corner. A pop-up box will display your resolution options. For most online purposes, a resolution of 150ppi is fine. If you’re going to print your presentation, choose the print 220ppi option. You can reduce the file size of all images in your presentation by selecting “**Apply to all pictures in the file**”.

Select ‘On-screen (150 ppi)’ picture quality for online purposes

By reducing the resolution of your images your image file sizes are limited, which means your presentation is no larger than it needs to be.

If you’re sending a document by email, convert your presentations into PDF format and use versions with reduced image resolution.

WORD DOCUMENT

To reduce image size in Microsoft Word:

1. Go to the “**File**” tab and select “**Reduce File Size**”.
2. In the pop-up box, select the resolution. For digital, use 150ppi and for printing, use 220ppi. You can reduce the file size of all images in your presentation by selecting “**Apply to all pictures in the file**”.

Select ‘Print (220 ppi)’ picture quality for print purposes

The IN-HABIT primary logo should always be used in Word documents.

 Download Word templates: <https://bit.ly/3cpodwL>

The IN-HABIT logo should be present in the top-left corner of every slide. The primary logo should always be used when the background is white. The white logo should always be used over a coloured background or image.

Download PowerPoint templates: <https://bit.ly/3cpodwL>

The white IN-HABIT logo can be used in the top-left corner of photography-based social media assets. The white logo should always be used over a coloured background or image.

When used over white, as in a title bar, the primary logo should be used. When used over an image, use the white logo.

[Visit the IN-HABIT website: https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/](https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/)

The roll up designs should follow the visual guidelines with the IN-HABIT logo always placed in the top half and the EU flag and accompanying copy placed at the bottom.

An example of a roll up design using photography

An example of a formal roll up design

Brochure design should follow the visual guidelines. Photography should be used in brochures only if the brochure will be professionally printed; otherwise, a single-coloured pattern should be used.

Below: An example of a brochure design using our brand pattern

Above: An example of a brochure design using photography

